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Adolescents' development of occupational aspirations in a tracked and vocation-oriented educational system

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1. Introduction

The formation of educational and occupational aspirations is an important developmental task during adolescence (Havighurst, 1952; Nurmi, 2004). Adolescents are expected to prepare for labour market entry and for becoming economically independent adults. This preparation requires a number of age-related educational and occupational decisions, which are guided by the construction of personal goals, such as occupational aspirations (Nurmi, 2004). The formation of these goals guides and directs adolescents' behaviour and effort (Boudrenghien, Frenay, Bourgeois, Karabenick, & Eccles, 2014), thus supporting their transition into post-compulsory education and training. This, in turn, is a prerequisite for stable integration into the labour market (Clausen, 1991; Heckhausen, Chang, Greenberger, & Chen, 2013). The literature has confirmed the crucial role of aspirations in this process by revealing that they serve as an important predictor of adult educational and occupational attainment (e.g., Beal & Crockett, 2010; Rojewski, 2005; Schoon, 2001; Schoon & Parsons, 2002).

Previous research has often focused on the formation of educational aspirations and expectations (e.g., Bandura, Barbaranelli, Caprara, & Pastorelli, 2001; Bozick, Alexander, Entwisle, Dauber, & Kerr, 2010; Buchmann & Dalton, 2002; Hegna, 2014; Johnson & Reynolds, 2013). Studies on the development of occupational aspirations, usually conceptualised by the status or prestige of the desired occupation, are less abundant. Work from the US and Britain reveals that youth generally develop fairly high and often unrealistic status aspirations (Furlong & Biggart, 1999; Reynolds, Stewart, MacDonald, & Sischo, 2006). Furthermore, most studies have found only modest changes in occupational status aspiration during adolescence, with stable or slightly decreasing status aspirations with increasing age (Beal & Crockett, 2010; Furlong & Biggart, 1999; Lee & Rojewski, 2009; Rojewski & Kim, 2003; Rojewski & Yang, 1997; Shapka, Domene, & Keating, 2006; Watson, Quatman, & Edler, 2002). This body of work also showed that the level and change of occupational aspirations depends on young people's socio-economic status (SES), school achievement, gender, and extracurricular activities.

A handful of German and Swiss studies have analysed the aspirational adaptation processes of youth bound for vocational education and training (VET), which is the dominant form of upper-secondary education in both countries. The results, based on short observation spans during lower secondary school, differ somewhat from those for the US and UK. In Germany and Switzerland between 14 and 16, most adolescents have already adapted their occupational aspirations to the perceived opportunities provided by their school environment (Heckhausen & Tomasik, 2002; Hirschi, 2010; Hirschi & Vondracek, 2009; Tomasik, Hardy, Haase, & Heckhausen, 2009). Hirschi and Vondracek (2009) also found that adolescents from lower-secondary school tracks with basic requirements adjusted their aspirations more strongly than did adolescents from tracks with advanced requirements.

Taken together, these findings imply that the development and adjustment of occupational status aspirations may be related to young people's social environment, which is defined by their socio-economic background and school environment. In countries such as Switzerland and Germany, the school environment is shaped by the track of lower- and upper-secondary school that is attended. The latter is linked to specific opportunities for higher education as well as specific job opportunities. However, previous research has either analysed the short-term influence of lower-secondary education only for selected groups of youth or focused on differences by socio-economic

status, gender, or school achievement. To our knowledge, no studies have systematically investigated the role of tracking and compared the development of occupational status aspirations between tracks of upper-secondary education over several years. We would like to address this gap by investigating how the allocation to specific secondary education tracks is related to the development of occupational aspirations. Switzerland is an ideal country in which to analyse this question. It features a highly stratified educational system with early tracking and limited permeability between tracks. Given that the upper-secondary tracks are related to specific opportunities for higher education and to specific job opportunities, we expect a close relationship between track placement and the development of occupational status aspirations.

We focus on adolescents between the age of 15 and 21 and on the status of the occupation to which they aspire. Status is related to the social rewards tied to an occupation, such as prestige, income, and opportunities for occupational mobility (Abraham, Damelang, & Schulz, 2011; Ganzeboom & Treiman, 2003). The development of occupational status aspirations is highly relevant to individual life chances. It has been identified by previous research as an important element of the social stratification mechanisms that lead to social inequality (e.g., Sewell, Haller, & Portes, 1969).

In the following sections, we first briefly describe the Swiss educational system. Second, we formulate hypotheses by drawing on both a social systems perspective (Dannefer, 1993) and an action-theoretical developmental approach (Heckhausen, 2002; Heckhausen & Shane 2015; Heckhausen & Buchmann 2018). After describing our data, variables and methods, we outline our results and conclude with their discussion.

2. Tracking in the Swiss educational system

Two features of the Swiss educational system are likely to matter for the development of occupational status aspirations: Firstly, secondary education is stratified and highly differentiated (Buchmann, Kriesi, Koomen, Imdorf, & Basler, 2016). Secondly, it is tightly linked with the labour market, which is segmented along occupational lines. Hence, access to most jobs is contingent upon holding the appropriate, often occupation-specific, educational credentials (Sacchi, Kriesi, & Buchmann, 2016).

Lower-secondary education, entered at the age of 12 or 13, is divided into several tracks, which differ by level of academic requirement (see Figure 1). It is followed by upper-secondary education, including baccalaureate schools, specialised schools, and vocational education and training (VET). Allocation to these tracks, taking place at about 15 years, depends on the lower-secondary school track and on grades (Buchmann et al., 2016).

Baccalaureate schools are only accessible to adolescents from lower-secondary tracks with high academic requirements and with good school grades. They allow direct access to academic universities. Specialised schools, leading to specialised baccalaureates, enable access to universities of applied science.

VET is the dominant type of Swiss upper-secondary education, chosen by about two thirds of a birth cohort. Although all levels of lower-secondary school allow access to VET, it is entered predominantly by young people from lower-secondary tracks with low or medium requirements.

Swiss VET is mostly firm-based, and trainees spend three to four days per week in the training firm and one to two days in vocational school. It is heterogeneous and offers approximately 230 training occupations, for which young people have to apply at the age of 14 or 15. The training occupations differ considerably in their intellectual requirements (Stalder, 2011). Whereas some require only basic maths and reading skills and teach manual or routine cognitive skills, others require advanced skills in maths, reading, and writing, including complex manual and analytical skills. Programmes requiring advanced skills are usually only accessible to adolescents who have completed lower-secondary tracks with high requirements.

Young people with VET diplomas may enter professional education at the tertiary level. Some earn a vocational baccalaureate, which is the entry ticket to universities of applied science. However, the chance of entering professional education and earning a vocational baccalaureate differs widely between the numerous VET programmes and is highest for adolescents in programmes with high intellectual requirements.

Although the Swiss educational system is nominally permeable, changes between tracks are rare. Furthermore, due to the tight link between the educational system and the occupationally segmented labour market, the choice of upper-secondary and tertiary track determines the range of occupations accessible in the labour market. High-status occupations, such as lawyer, biologist, and medical doctor, require a university degree. The majority of occupations in the medium range of the status scale, such as social workers, primary school teacher, technician, and master craftsperson, require professional education or a university of applied sciences degree. Vocational education and training diplomas allow access to jobs in the lower status range, such as hairdresser, house painter, and sales assistant. In the following section, we explain our assumptions about the likely relationship between these features of the educational system and the formation of occupational status aspirations.

3. Theoretical assumptions

We define occupational aspirations as an individual's *goals regarding his or her future career* (see, e.g., Lent, Brown, & Hackett, 1994, p.85; Rojewski, 2005, p.132). The formation of these goals or aspirations is a dynamic process, and young people construct and reconstruct them in relation to upcoming transitions and changing social environments (Nurmi, 2004). Consequently, aspirations are not stable over the early life course (Cantor, 1990; Gottfredson, 1981; Vondracek, Lerner, & Schulenberg, 1986). They are formed in childhood but remain fairly vague and unrelated to realistic options and opportunities until early adolescence (Gottfredson, 1981). From this period, adolescents' future-oriented cognitions change. They become more realistic, form their own identity and interests, and gather experiences in various social contexts (Beal & Crockett, 2010; Eccles, Barber, Stone, & Hunt, 2003; Gottfredson, 2005; Rojewski, 2005). From early adolescence, young people also become increasingly aware of the opportunities and constraints provided by their social environment (Gottfredson, 2005). Taking these opportunities and constraints into account when planning for the future is one of the developmental tasks faced in this phase of life (Nurmi, 1993, 2004).

3.1 Educational tracks, opportunities and aspirations and individual development

From a social systems perspective, human action is systematically embedded in a stratified social system, which provides specific resources for individual development as well as stimuli and messages about the value of developmental outcomes. Characteristics of an individual's social context therefore not only affect his or her opportunities in life but also translate into physical and psychological differences, including social developmental trajectories (Dannefer, 1992).

The educational context and its structure, such as the number and nature of school tracks, is of particular relevance to the formation of occupational status aspirations. Track allocation and the concomitant institutional structures of educational tracks assign individuals to particular roles and positions within the system (Dannefer, 1992). The resultant opportunity structure is fairly transparent for adolescents (Hamilton, 1994). It impacts young people's developmental outcomes and pathways by shaping their performance gains and the perception of their abilities and options (Dannefer, 1992; Gamoran, 1996; Heckhausen & Buchmann, 2018; Heckhausen & Shane, 2015; Person, Rosenbaum, & Deil-Amen, 2005). Heckhausen and Buchmann (2018, p. 7) call this process "societal canalisation". According to this line of reasoning, adolescents internalise the personal qualities and expectations that are deemed appropriate for their school type and academic performance and attainment (Meyer, 1977/2007). Consequently, aspirations and goals are aligned with the opportunities perceived at a specific stage in the educational career (Heckhausen & Buchmann, 2018; Heckhausen & Shane, 2015). In line with this assumption, Hirschi (2010) found that by the age of about 14 years, Swiss adolescents have already adapted their aspirations to the opportunities offered by their social environment.

3.2 Adaptation mechanism of occupational status aspirations in tracked school systems

In order to formulate hypotheses how the process of societal canalisation influences the formation of aspirations in a tracked school system, some aspects of Heckhausen's (2002) action-phase model of developmental regulation are useful. The model assumes that processes of goal formation differ before and after developmental deadlines, such as the transition to lower or upper-secondary education. Before transition deadlines, individuals are engaged in goal formation and goal striving. Once the deadline has passed and the individual has failed to reach his or her goals, processes of goal disengagement, compromise, and the formation of less demanding goals are set in motion. If an individual has reached the set goals successfully, his or her action resources are strengthened. Furthermore, successful transitions lead to changes in the social context. Such changes trigger self-induced adaptation processes because individuals assess new alternatives and courses of action (see also Heinz, Kelle, & Witzel, 1998). Consequently, individuals may set new and possibly more ambitious goals.

Based on this model, Tomasić, Hardy, Haase and Heckhausen (2009) argue that young people face two potentially contradictory objectives when developing and channelling their aspirations before a transition deadline. The occupation aspired to should be accessible with the credentials and school grades held and thus reflect a certain degree of realism. At the same time, it should serve to maximise the social prestige attainable. To meet these objectives, the process of developing aspirations before an approaching transition is characterised by two consecutive mechanisms or steps. In the first, it is rational for young people to aim high and to develop comparatively high status aspirations

to maximise both the attainment probability and the social prestige of occupational goals (Tomasik et al., 2009). In the second step, as the transition deadline approaches, processes of compromise may lead to the exclusion of options perceived as inaccessible and to a subsequent decrease of occupational status aspirations. After the successful transition to upper-secondary education, adolescents resume the process of occupational goal formation. Occupational status aspirations may be raised again due to the perception of new opportunities and increased individual resources (Tomasik et al., 2009).

3.3 Differences in the development of occupational status aspirations by secondary track

Although the Swiss educational system is nominally very permeable and allows changes between tracks, such changes are rare. Track placement from the age of 12 onwards thus strongly affects young people's opportunities for further education and employment and shapes their horizon of possibilities. It also shapes the temporal exigencies of the goal-setting process, because the allocation to different tracks goes along with different developmental deadlines for occupational decisions. We argue that the process of societal canalisation and therefore also the process of adapting occupational status aspirations depends on young people's lower-secondary and initial upper-secondary track allocations and on their subsequent educational trajectories.

Young people who are allocated to tracks of lower-secondary education with low or medium requirements are channelled into vocational education and training (Buchmann et al., 2016). In contrast to young people on tracks with high requirements, who may enter baccalaureate school, those on low-requirement tracks face the task of developing clear occupational goals at the early age of 14 or 15, when they attempt to secure an occupation-specific apprenticeship position within a firm. Furthermore, their opportunities are constrained to the range of VET programmes potentially attainable with their lower-secondary track and grades. Consequently, the process of compromise is likely to be severe, and the concomitant decrease of aspirations will have taken place before the age of 15. *We thus assume that adolescents in lower-secondary tracks with low academic requirements have formed considerably lower aspirations than have their counterparts in high-requirement tracks (Hypothesis 1).* We expect a similar mechanism to be at work regarding track placement in upper-secondary school. Although all types of regular upper-secondary diplomas allow entry into higher education, young people who trained in VET programmes with lower intellectual requirements face higher entry hurdles than those who trained in programmes with higher requirements. The latter have easier access to professional education and to universities of applied sciences but face obstacles regarding access to academic universities. We assume that adolescents take these odds and opportunities into account when setting their goals after the transition to upper-secondary education. We therefore hypothesise that *adolescents in baccalaureate school will have higher aspirations than will those with a specialised or vocational baccalaureate or VET with high academic requirements. The latter's aspirations are higher than those of adolescents with VET with low academic requirements (Hypothesis 2).*

For young people who enter VET, the transition to upper-secondary education marks an important developmental deadline and focal point for the development of aspirations. After the successful mastery of this deadline, the process of goal setting is likely to be resumed. It will be influenced by the growing work experience and knowledge regarding further career opportunities and options for tertiary-level training (Heinz et al., 1998).

This broadening of perspectives after entry into upper-secondary education is likely to trigger self-induced adaptation processes (Heinz, 2000) and an increase in status aspirations (Heckhausen, 2006). Hence, we assume that *adolescents who enter vocational education and training increase their occupational status aspirations after the age of 15 (Hypothesis 3).*

Young people entering baccalaureate school have more time and leeway for the formation of concrete aspirations. They face their first developmental deadline regarding occupational aspirations at the age of about 18, when they have to decide whether to enter the labour market or to choose a field of study. Furthermore, their occupational opportunities are formally less restricted because the majority of study fields are accessible with an academic baccalaureate. Access to select fields of study, such as medicine and some art colleges, is limited by entry exams. However, the successful completion of specific tertiary-level fields of studies is contingent upon field-specific academic performance. The successful study of sciences or economics, for example, requires a high level of maths performance. We therefore assume that young people in baccalaureate school maintain high status aspirations after the transition to upper-secondary education but start to engage in the process of compromise as the transition deadline approaches towards the end of baccalaureate school. We therefore expect *a decline in the occupational status aspirations of baccalaureate students, which is likely to occur at 17 or 18 years of age (Hypothesis 4).*

After initial track allocation, the majority of students complete their upper-secondary education as planned. A sizeable minority change their initial track. Within the framework of Heckhausen's (2002) action-phase model, a track change is comparable to passing a developmental deadline. The transition to a new track will trigger motivational processes leading to an adaptation of aspirations. This is particularly likely if the status of the initial aspirations is incompatible with the opportunities provided by the new track of upper-secondary education. Depending on the status of the new track, adolescents may then perceive aspirations as inappropriate due to their low status, or they may perceive the aspirations to be as inaccessible because the adolescents lack credentials, abilities, or resources, thus requiring compromises. We hypothesise that *changes into a lower track of upper-secondary education or into a vocational programme with lower intellectual requirements be accompanied by aspirational downgrading or "cooling out" (Hypothesis 5a), as Alexander, Bozick and Entwisle (2008) have termed this process. Changing to a higher track or a vocational programme with higher intellectual abilities will lead to aspirational upgrading (Hypothesis 5b).*

Before turning to our data and methods, a few remarks regarding our control variables are in order. Previous research has revealed that the development of occupational aspirations depends on adolescents' socio-economic background, educational achievement, gender, and ethnicity. A number of studies have shown that adolescents from families with a low socio-economic background develop lower status aspirations and decrease their aspirations more across time than do those from higher SES families (Furlong & Biggart, 1999; Rojewski & Kim, 2003; Rojewski & Yang, 1997). Similarly, youth with higher academic achievement develop higher status aspirations (Hirschi & Vondracek, 2009; Rojewski & Yang, 1997; Shapka et al., 2006; Watson et al., 2002). Girls and minority students often develop higher status aspirations than do boys and non-minority students respectively (Furlong & Biggart, 1999; Lee & Rojewski, 2009). Given the relevance of these variables, we control for them in our model.

4. Data and Methods

4.1 Data

We based our analyses on the adolescent cohort of the *Swiss Longitudinal Survey of Children and Youth* (COCON). The data are representative of the German- and French-speaking parts of Switzerland.¹ The adolescents, born between 1 September 1990 and 30 April 1991, were surveyed in 2006, 2007, 2009, and 2012 at the ages of 15, 16, 18, and 21 respectively through computer-assisted personal interviews.² The data include respondents' educational or occupational pathways, social background, socialisation contexts, and the development of informal competencies.

The first data wave included 1257 individuals. The numbers of participants in the second, third, and fourth waves were 1162, 952, and 816 respectively. We excluded all individuals who made the transition to upper-secondary education after the age of 18 ($N = 54$)³ and those with missing values, which left us with a sample of 1011 participants for the first wave (54% female). Because multilevel models for panel data do not require complete data for all time points (Hoffman, 2015), the number of individuals per time point differs ("unbalanced" final sample, see also Table 1) and includes a total of 3294 observations and 3.3 time points per individual on average.

In order to rule out a sample bias due to attrition, we employed two strategies. We compared participants and non-participants of the first and the fourth waves regarding the main variables included in the model. The results showed that participants from less demanding types of lower-secondary and lower upper-secondary school tracks and with lower occupational status aspirations were more likely to drop out before wave four (see Table 2).⁴ In addition, we applied multiple imputation (see Allison, 2001; Asendorpf, Van De Schoot, Denissen, & Hutteman, 2014; Ferro, 2014; Graham, 2009) and compared the models with and without imputed values.⁵ The results were highly similar. Consequently, we estimated our final models without imputed data.⁶

¹ The sample was drawn by a two-stage method in which 131 communities (broken down by community type and community size) were selected. Adolescents living in these communities were randomly sampled based on official residence registers.

² The second wave (16 years) is based on computer-assisted telephone interviews.

³ In Switzerland, only few young people never enter upper-secondary education. Most of those who remain without an upper-secondary credential (about 10%) do so because they drop out of vocational education and training or fail the final upper-secondary exams (Buchmann, 2013).

⁴ Regarding our control variables, attrition was higher for young adults from families with lower socio-economic status, with a migration background, lower school performance and lower basic cognitive abilities.

⁵ The imputation procedure is based on the assumption that missing data are missing at random (MAR) and depend only on observed variables. MAR assumes that potential biases caused by systematic attrition can be corrected by imputing missing values based on existing data. Missing values are replaced by values that have been estimated with observed variables (Asendorpf et al., 2014; Graham, 2009). We imputed each missing value 20 times and combined the separate results (see Eddings & Marchenko, 2012). No auxiliary variables were used in the imputation model.

⁶ The models based on imputed data are available on request from the authors.

4.2 Measures

4.2.1 Dependent and independent variables

The dependent variable captures the status of the respondents' occupational aspirations in all four data waves. The respondents were asked for which occupation they would like to train if they could choose freely. We assigned the answers to the eight-digit code of the Swiss Standard Classification of Occupations 2000.⁷ In a next step, we matched the occupational codes with the international socio-economic index of occupational status (ISEI) (Ganzeboom, De Graaf, & Treiman, 1992). In contrast to other measures, such as the Treiman prestige scale and Erikson and Goldthorpe's class categories, the ISEI captures the status of an occupation continuously and includes more than one status dimension (i.e., education and income). The range of the ISEI reaches from 16 to 90, with farm-hands, laborers, and cleaners at the lowest end and judges at the highest end (Ganzeboom et al., 1992).

The variable for lower-secondary school distinguishes four tracks: lower-secondary schools with low, medium, or high requirements or without tracking (comprehensive type). This is a time-constant predictor measured at the age of 15.

The variable for upper-secondary school captures the first track of upper-secondary education after completion of lower-secondary school. Three categories are distinguished: vocational education and training with low or medium intellectual requirements (VET-); vocational education and training with high intellectual requirements, including specialised and vocational baccalaureate schools (VET+)⁸; and academic baccalaureate schools. The distinction between VET with low, medium, and high requirements is based on Stalder's (2011) expert rating of a vocational programme's overall intellectual requirements. It distinguishes six categories: VET with high requirements includes programmes of the two highest intellectual requirement levels, 5 and 6; VET with low and medium requirements combines the low and medium requirement levels, 1 to 4.

Two time-dependent dummy variables capture whether young people changed track after the transition to upper-secondary education and if yes, in which direction. Adolescents who changed to a higher track after their first entry into upper-secondary education (e.g., a change from VET to baccalaureate school) were coded as 1 on the "upwards" dummy variable in the wave after the change. Those who changed into a lower track (e.g., change from baccalaureate school to a specialised school or VET) were coded as 1 on the "downward" variable in the wave after the change took place. Adolescents with stable track allocation serve as reference group for both dummy variables.

Lastly, we included time as a centred indicator for the observation years 2006, 2007, 2009, and 2012 with the proportional values 0 for the first survey wave, 1 for the second, 3 for the third, and 6 for the fourth survey wave. We also employ the time indicator to capture the random slope.

4.2.2 Control variables

⁷ Two independent raters coded the occupational information. Inter-rater reliability was above 95%; unclear cases were re-evaluated by a third party.

⁸ Only 18% of the adolescents in this category have entered a specialized school. For simplicity, will thus refer to this group as adolescents' in VET+.

We controlled for SES, school grades, gender, basic cognitive abilities, migration background, and labour market entry. In order to measure SES, we make use of the parents' highest educational level, distinguishing between families in which at least one of the parents has tertiary-level education (1) and those in which both parents have no more than upper-secondary-level education (0). The information stems from the first data wave, and the indicator is time constant.

We measure school performance at the age of 15 with the centred average of the grades in mathematics and the local language (German or French), because the track placement within the Swiss educational system is strongly based on these two grades (Buchmann et al. 2016). Their values range from 1 to 6, with 6 being the highest possible score. Gender is coded with 0 for women and 1 for men. Basic cognitive abilities were measured at the age of 15. The indicator is based on the short version of a non-verbal basic intelligence test (CFT 1, see Cattell, Weiss, & Osterland, 1977), with values ranging from 0 to 6 (centred variable). Migration background distinguishes between adolescents with Swiss nationality (0) and those without (1). We also controlled whether an individual had already entered the labour market at wave four (1) or not (0). Table 1 shows the descriptives for all variables.

4.3 Analytical strategy and model fit

Our analyses are based on linear multilevel models with a repeated-measurement design (e.g., Hoffman, 2015; Rabe-Hesketh & Skrondal, 2012). The multilevel model takes into account the fact that individual status scores at ages 15, 16, 18 and 21 are nested within the individual. Consequently, intra-individual model residuals will be correlated (e.g., Hoffman, 2015; Macmillan, McMorris, & Kruttschnitt, 2004).⁹ As young adults may differ in their development of status aspirations (Macmillan & Furstenberg, 2016), we added a random slope for time to our model, allowing the covariate effects to vary across individuals.¹⁰

First, we calculated a random slope model. Then, with the aim of analysing the change of occupational status aspirations for different educational tracks over time, we estimated a growth curve model. We did this by including an interaction term for upper-secondary education and time in our random slope model (see also Macmillan & Furstenberg, 2016). In both models, survey waves were assigned to level 1 and individuals to level 2. Level 1 predicts the outcome variation within individuals over time and level 2 the variation between individuals (Hoffman, 2015; Raudenbush & Bryk, 2002), resulting in the following equations for our random slope model:

$$\text{Level 1: } y_{ji} = \beta_{0i} + \beta_{1i}(\text{time}_{ij}) + \varepsilon_{ij}$$

$$\text{Level 2: } \beta_{0i} = \gamma_{00} + \zeta_{0i}$$

⁹ The intra-class correlation coefficient (ICC) of our empty model including time showed variance between and within individuals (58% and 42% respectively), thus indicating that a multilevel model is appropriate (Hoffman, 2015; Hosoya, Koch, & Eid, 2014).

¹⁰ A random slope represents our data more accurately, as shown by a likelihood ratio test. This test showed that by adding a random slope, the log likelihood of the model increased significantly (LR ($\chi^2 = 38.43$, $p = .000$) (see Hoffman, 2015; Rabe-Hesketh & Skrondal, 2012).

$$\beta_{1i} = \gamma_{10} + \varsigma_{1i}$$

$$\text{Composite: } y_{ji} = (\gamma_{00} + \varsigma_{0i}) + (\gamma_{10} + \varsigma_{1i})(time_{ij}) + \varepsilon_{ij}$$

Our dependent variable y_{ji} at time j for individual i is a function of the individual intercept β_{0i} , a fixed linear effect of time and a time-specific and person-specific residual ε_{ij} , whereby β_{0i} is defined by the fixed intercept γ_{00} and its individual-specific random intercept ς_{0i} . The term β_{1i} is composed of a fixed linear slope for time γ_{10} and a random slope for time ς_{1i} . By including ς_{0i} and ς_{1i} at level 2, each individual is allocated his or her own intercept and own slope for time (Hoffman, 2015).

Our random slope model with covariates may be summarised as follows:

$$\begin{aligned} ISEI_{ij} = & \beta_{00} + \beta_1(time_{ij}) + \beta_2(lower\text{-}sec.\text{track}_i) + \beta_3(upper\text{-}sec.\text{track}_i) \\ & + \beta_4(downwards_{ij}) + \beta_5(upwards_{ij}) + \varsigma_{0i} + \varsigma_{1i}(time_{ij}) + \varepsilon_{ij} \end{aligned}$$

The $ISEI_{ij}$ is the observed value of the occupational status aspiration for individual i at time j . It is defined by the intercept β_{00} (i.e. the mean of the dependent variable over the entire sample and all time points, which captures the expected outcome when all variables are zero¹¹) and the covariates $\beta_1(time_{ij}) + \beta_2(lower\text{-}sec.\text{track}_i) + \beta_3(upper\text{-}sec.\text{track}_i) + \beta_4(downwards_{ij}) + \beta_5(upwards_{ij})$. This represents the fixed part of the model. The sum of $\varsigma_{0i} + \varsigma_{1i}(time_{ij}) + \varepsilon_{ij}$ represents the random model part, whereby ς_{0i} captures the deviation of individual i from the mean intercept β_{00} and $\varsigma_{1i}(time_{ij})$ captures the deviation of the individual-specific slope from the mean slope of time. The term ε_{ij} is the level 1 residual that captures the time-specific deviation of each person-specific mean (Hoffman, 2015; Macmillan & Furstenberg, 2016; Rabe-Hesketh & Skrondal, 2012).

The growth curve model, which represents a random slope model with an additional interaction term between time and upper-secondary track, may be summarised as follows:

$$\begin{aligned} ISEI_{ij} = & \beta_{00} + \beta_1(time_{ij}) + \beta_2(lower\text{-}sec.\text{track}_i) + \beta_3(upper\text{-}sec.\text{track}_i) \\ & + \beta_6(upper\text{-}sec.\text{track}_i * time_{ij}) + \varsigma_{0i} + \varsigma_{1i}(time_{ij}) + \varepsilon_{ij} \end{aligned}$$

¹¹ Consequently, the intercept of the full model including all predictors estimated the occupational status aspirations of a 15-year-old Swiss-born girl who attends a lower-secondary school track with high requirements, showed average school performance, entered baccalaureate school, had no subsequent track changes, and is endowed with average basic cognitive abilities.

We analysed our data with the Stata (version 13) software package and applied a two level-hierarchical structure, using the “mixed” command. The figures show marginal effects and were created using Stata’s “marginsplot” command. We used the restricted maximum likelihood estimators (reml) and applied an unstructured covariance structure.

5. Results

The results of the multilevel models are presented in Table 3. First, we considered the impact of our independent variables on the average occupational status aspirations across all four time points. After estimating the empty model, we added the predictor and control variables stepwise, beginning with upper-secondary track and time only (RCM1). Model RCM2 also includes the upper-secondary track before all other covariates are included, as they are in RCM3. Second, the growth curve model (GCM) estimates the trajectories of the upper-secondary tracks over time (see also Figure 2).

5.1 Determinants of the average level of occupational status aspirations

The empty model showed that the fixed effect of time was positive and amounted to 0.36 status points (β : 0.36, $p < 0.003$). The random part of our model indicated that both the error variance of the random slope and the random intercept were significant at the 5% level. Consequently, the effects between time points and between individuals differed significantly. The 95% confidence intervals of the random intercept and random slope indicated that 95% of our participants had individual intercepts ranging from 25.40 to 80.48 status points and random time slopes from -3.23 to 3.94 status points.¹² Based on the variation of the time slope, we conclude that the significant average increase of occupational status aspirations over time could not be observed for all individuals. In the full random coefficient model (RCM3), the linear effect of time remained significant. On average, occupational status aspirations thus rose significantly over time (β : 0.44, $p < 0.000$).

In line with Hypothesis 1, adolescents’ aspirations were linked with their track of lower-secondary education. Adolescents from lower-secondary schools with high requirements, our reference group, had the highest occupational status aspirations of all groups. Those in medium-level tracks, and particularly those in lower-level tracks, had lower occupational status aspirations (see RCM1, Table 3). Although the effects became considerably weaker after controlling for upper-secondary education (see RCM2), they did not lose their predictive power completely. The difference between the highest and the

¹² *Random effect 95% CI = fixed effect \pm (1.96 * SD)* (see Hoffman, 2015; Snijders & Bosker, 1999).

lowest levels (RCM3: β : -4.42, $p < 0.034$) and between the highest and the medium levels remained significant (RCM3: β : -1.61, $p < 0.053$).

The findings for the upper-secondary track showed that compared to young people who entered academic baccalaureate school (reference group), all other groups had significantly lower occupational status aspirations. Adolescents in baccalaureate schools aspired to occupations whose status was, on average, more than 16 points higher than those aspired to by young people with vocational education and training with low or medium requirements (VET-) and about nine points higher than the status aspirations of young people in VET with high intellectual requirements (VET+). Taking into account that the average status score of the sample, which amounts to almost 53 points, these differences between tracks are large. To compare the two vocational groups directly, we ran the model with VET- as the reference group. The findings showed that young people in VET+ aspired to occupations with about six and a half points higher status than did those in VET- (RCM3: β : 6.533, $p < 0.000$, results not shown). A comparison of RCM2 and RCM3 also showed that the effect of upper-secondary education remained stable even after including our control variables. Consequently, the differences in status aspirations between upper-secondary tracks are not due to differences between the adolescents in SES, school performance, basic cognitive abilities, or migration background.

In line with Hypothesis 5a, adolescents who changed to a lower upper-secondary track featured lower occupational status aspirations than the reference group with consistent upper-secondary track allocation. The average difference is considerable and amounts to over five points on the status scale (RCM3: β : -5.21, $p < 0.000$). Those who changed to a more demanding track after initial track allocation upgraded their status aspirations slightly (Hypothesis 5b). However, the effect is not significant (RCM: β : 0.40, $p < 0.808$).

[About here: Table 3: Multilevel models: Determinants of occupational status aspirations]

5.2 The development of occupational status aspirations between 15 and 21 years: results of the growth curve model

The test of our Hypotheses 3 and 4 on the development of status aspirations across time is based on the interaction of time with the upper-secondary school track in the growth curve model (see Table 3). Both interaction terms were statistically significant. Figure 2 provides an overview of the aspiration trajectories. The findings showed that the development of occupational status aspirations between the age of 15 and 21 differed markedly between young people who entered baccalaureate school and those who entered VET+ and VET-.

From the main effect of the upper-secondary track, we conclude that at the age of 15 young people in baccalaureate school had occupational status aspirations which were, on average, about 18 points higher on the status scale than those of their counterparts bound for VET with low/medium requirements (GCM: β : -18.32, $p < 0.000$). The difference from young people bound for VET with high requirements amounted to over 11 points (GCM:

β : -11.60, $p < 0.000$). After the age of 15, adolescents who entered baccalaureate school lowered their status aspirations, which is in line with Hypothesis 4. The main effect of the indicator for time showed that the average annual downwards trend was -0.37 status points for this group, which was significant at the 10 percent level (GCM: β : -0.37, $p < 0.064$).

[About here: Figure 2: Development of occupation aspirations by upper-secondary school track]

In contrast to young people in baccalaureate school, both groups of adolescents in vocational education and training programmes increased their aspirations over time. This is in line with our Hypothesis 3 and holds particularly for adolescents in VET with low or medium requirements. This group increased their aspirations by 0.78 points per year (VET-: β 1.15 - 0.37 = 0.78, $p < 0.000$). By the age of 21 years, their occupational status aspirations were almost five points higher than at the age of 15. Adolescents in vocational education and training with high requirements increased their aspirations on average by 0.58 status points per year (β : VET+: 0.95 - 0.37 = 0.58, $p < 0.001$). Figure 2 also shows that occupational status aspirations between young people in different upper-secondary tracks converged slightly with increasing age. The differences were largest at the age of 15 and smallest by age 21, although they remained sizeable and statistically significant.

The results for our control variables showed, in line with previous research, (e.g., Beal & Crockett, 2010; Schoon, 2001; Schoon & Parsons, 2002; Schoon & Polek, 2011; Sewell et al., 1969), that young people from high SES families had higher occupational status aspirations, even after controlling for school performance and track allocation. Occupational status aspirations were also significantly higher for young people with higher school performance at the end of compulsory education. Men showed significantly higher occupational status aspirations than women. Neither basic cognitive abilities nor migration background were related significantly to the level of average status aspirations.

6. Discussion

This study investigated the development of occupational status aspirations over the course of six years from adolescence to early adulthood. We have used Switzerland as an example, because it features a strongly tracked educational system with a tight link to the labour market. The dominance of vocational education and training at the upper-secondary level implies that the majority of adolescents face the task of developing concrete occupational status aspirations at the young age of 13 or 14 years (see also Hirschi & Vondracek, 2009). Given that opportunities for educational and occupational attainment are strongly and transparently determined by the tracks of lower- and upper-secondary education, our basic claim was that the level and development of adolescents' occupational status aspirations are closely linked to adolescents' educational pathways in lower- and upper-secondary school.

The relationship between track allocation and the status level of occupational aspirations is surprisingly pronounced and clear-cut. In line with our theoretical

assumptions, the findings suggest that adolescents align their occupational status aspirations with the perceived opportunities tied to their educational track. This is already apparent at the end of lower-secondary school. At this stage of their life course, most boys and girls seem to have discarded their dream notions of possible future occupations and have adjusted their aspirations to the more realistic options offered by their lower-secondary track. The fact that the lower-secondary track remains influential even after controlling for the upper-secondary track supports the assumption that by assigning individuals to particular roles and positions in the social system early tracking has a very strong and long-lasting impact on young people's perception of their occupational options. This in turn has serious implications for social inequality.

After the transition to the upper-secondary level, this track takes centre stage in the formation of occupational status aspirations. It orders the average level of occupational status aspiration hierarchically. Two aspects deserve emphasis: Firstly, the prospective allocation to baccalaureate schools seems to be the main driver for aspiring to top-level occupations. In the fairly transparent Swiss educational system, young people bound for academic baccalaureate schools are likely to be aware that their path of upper-secondary education is not aimed at direct labour market entry but at university admission. Consequently, they anticipate higher education leading to concomitant high-status jobs. Secondly, the two VET groups differ considerably in the average level of their status aspirations, and allocation to VET with low or medium intellectual requirements has a remarkably strong curbing effect on aspirations, particularly before the transition to upper-secondary education. This is likely due to the low status of the training occupations accessible. However, the options for further tertiary-level training differ between the two VET groups. Young people who train in VET programmes with high requirements have considerably better chances of earning a vocational baccalaureate and of entering a university of applied science. Holders of VET degrees with medium or low requirements more often enter higher vocational education, which leads to occupations with, on average, lower status. This interpretation is also consistent with previous findings from Buchmann et al. (2016), who showed that vocational programmes offer unequal opportunities and should not be treated as a homogenous category. Taken together, these results are in line with the notion of societal canalisation (Heckhausen & Buchmann, 2018). They support the assumption that from early adolescence onwards, the school track that young people are allocated to shapes their perceived abilities, their motivation and their perceived opportunities. In turn, these factors lead to the formation of aspirations that young people deem appropriate for their school type.

Based on Heckhausen's (2002) model of developmental regulation, we argued that the process of goal formation differs before and after developmental deadlines requiring occupational decisions. Consequently, we expected differences in the aspiration trajectories of young people in baccalaureate school and in VET between the ages of 15 and 21. Our results support this assumption. Whereas the former lower their occupational status aspirations during this life phase, the latter, particularly young people in VET with low or medium requirements, increase their aspirations considerably. The pattern is in line with Tomasik and colleagues' (2009) assumption that in order to maximise their attainable social prestige, adolescents develop high status aspirations at first and lower them before a transition deadline to occupational options that are perceived as accessible. Once the deadline has passed, aspirations are adjusted anew to the changed circumstances.

Our results suggest that young people who enter VET are likely to use upper-secondary training occupations as reference points when forming their aspirations. They

are forced to make an early choice of occupation, which leaves little room and energy for further planning. Moreover, the tertiary-level opportunities for people with VET are less transparent and more diverse than the institutionalised options for academic baccalaureate holders. Consequently, the upper-secondary training occupations on offer shape vocational education trainees' perceived options and aspirations before the transition to upper-secondary education. After a successful transition, young people's action resources increase, and they begin to adapt their occupational status aspirations to their training environment. This environment is characterised by practical work in the training firm alongside experienced adult workers with varying educational and occupational backgrounds. Consequently, VET trainees gain work experience as well as knowledge about the world of work, including an awareness that a vocational upper-secondary diploma offers only limited opportunities for earnings and mobility. Furthermore, VET trainees learn more about options for further education and career development, which lead to the formation of more ambitious occupational goals.

Young people in baccalaureate school approach the developmental deadline requiring occupational choices several years later at the end of upper-secondary education. The downward trend in their aspirational status is likely to reflect processes of compromise setting in with the approaching deadline. Some baccalaureate students may realise that they are unlikely to succeed in the tertiary pathway to which they aspire or in finding a job in their desired occupation due to lacking grades or abilities. Consequently, they compromise and adjust their aspirations to their perceived opportunities.

Finally, the proposed adaptation mechanisms and the power of secondary school tracks in shaping occupational status aspirations are also apparent in the finding that adolescents who change to a lower track after the transition to upper-secondary education tend to adjust their aspirations accordingly. These track changes are likely to shift the focal point for the development of aspirations and trigger motivational processes that lead to an adaptation of occupational status aspirations.

6.1 Limitations

Despite several strengths, this study is not without limitations. Firstly, we are unable to observe the adaptation process we have postulated for young people bound for VET, which happens before the age of 15 and thus cannot be observed with our data. However, this process has been documented by previous research (Tomasik et al., 2009; Hirschi, 2010; Hirschi & Vondracek, 2009). We have no reason to believe that our data would show a different pattern.

Secondly, we are unable to determine causality with absolute certainty. We cannot fully discount the possibility that occupational status aspirations may affect adolescents' choice of lower- and upper-secondary tracks rather than vice versa. However, given that the allocation to lower-secondary school at the age of 12 is strongly determined by academic performance in primary school, it is not particularly plausible to assume that occupational status aspirations at this age have much of an impact on track allocation. We think that it is more plausible that tracking affects occupational status aspirations. Moreover, causality inference between track placement and the development of occupational status aspirations is limited because our data does not allow a direct test of the proposed individual-level mechanisms, which are likely to lead to different outcomes in the formation and development of occupational status aspirations. Consequently, we

cannot discount the possibility that unobserved factors affect both track placement and the development of occupational status aspirations (see also Sobel, 2013).

7. Conclusions

This study investigated young people's occupational status aspirations in a strongly stratified and tracked educational system. It contributes to a better understanding of the role of tracking in explaining the level and development of status aspirations during adolescence. The longitudinal design, which includes four measurement points, allowed us to go beyond existing research and to provide insights into track-dependent aspirational trajectories from the end of lower-secondary school to the beginning of higher education or labour market entry.

In sum, the strong and clear-cut relationship between track allocation and adolescents' levels of occupational status aspirations suggests that track allocation is crucial for the development of aspirations, at least in differentiated and stratified educational systems. From a theoretical perspective, the results support our claim that individual action and development is intertwined with the structure of the social system and the opportunities it provides. The latter shape individuals' perceptions (see Dannefer, 1992; Gamoran, 1996; Heckhausen & Buchmann, 2018; Person et al., 2005) and lead to the internalisation of personal skills and expectations that are considered appropriate for adolescents' upper-secondary tracks and their academic performance (Meyer, 1977/2007). The mechanism of societal canalisation (Heckhausen & Buchmann, 2018) explains the tight link between secondary school tracks and the development of occupational status aspirations. However, this link is not static, it depends on the stage in the life course and the concomitant developmental deadlines, as proposed by Heckhausen's (2002) action-phase model of developmental regulation. In line with this assumption, the findings imply that adolescents adjust the development of their aspirations to the perceived success or failure of the past transition as well as to the opportunities provided by the approaching deadline.

Our findings have three implications for social inequality. Firstly, bearing in mind that aspirations are one of the most influential determinants for attainment, the results highlight the important role of tracking in explaining unequal occupational attainment in adulthood. Secondly, the findings illustrate that early tracking is accompanied by simultaneous aspirational adjustment. In Switzerland, this societal canalisation of the school system sets in very early. It leads to a curbing or promotion of occupational status aspirations, which set in at the age of 11 or 12, when children are allocated to the lower-secondary school track. Thirdly, in light of the strong relationship between status aspirations and school tracks, track permeability may be important for the long-term consequences of occupational status aspirations. Due to the tight link between the educational system and the labour market, pronounced changes to chosen education and career pathways are costly and thus fairly difficult to achieve. To ensure that early track placement does not rigidly lock students into aspiration and attainment trajectories, an educational system should provide options for track changes. Preferably, these options do not require substantial financial and time resources and are easy to reach.

Future research would benefit from extending the observation span, including both the transition to lower upper-secondary school and the time span of early adulthood, when young people typically undergo either higher education or stable labour market integration.

Furthermore, the motivational adaptation mechanisms proposed by this study need further investigation. This pertains to knowledge gains regarding future educational and occupational opportunities, to the development of skills and competences during upper-secondary education, to the quality of the learning environment, and to changing interests, self-concepts, and job values, which may trigger the adaptation processes observed in this study. A qualitative design or a more in-depth quantitative study focusing on the educational environment would suit this avenue of research.

ACCEPTED MANUSCRIPT

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Tables and Figures

Table 1: Descriptive statistics

	N	Missings	Mean	Std. Dev.	Min	Max
<i>Time-variant variables - wave 1</i>						
Status of occupational aspirations (ISEI)	1132	71	51.84	17.97	19.00	90.00
Changes in upper-secondary track allocation (ref. stable)						
Downwards	1203	0	0.00	0.00	0	0
Upwards	1203	0	0.00	0.00	0	0
<i>Time-variant variables - wave 2</i>						
Status of occupational aspirations (ISEI)	1014	189	51.75	18.21	19.00	90.00
Changes in upper-secondary track allocation (ref. stable)						
Downwards	1118	85	0.00	0.03	0	1
Upwards	1118	85	0.00	0.05	0	1
<i>Time-variant variables - wave 3</i>						
Status of occupational aspirations (ISEI)	814	389	55.17	17.30	16.00	88.00
Changes in upper-secondary track allocation (ref. stable)						
Downwards	898	450	0.04	0.19	0	1
Upwards	898	450	0.02	0.13	0	1
<i>Time-variant variables - wave 4</i>						
Status of occupational aspirations (ISEI)	652	551	54.63	16.82	23.00	90.00
Changes in upper-secondary track allocation (ref. stable)						
Downwards	753	450	0.15	0.36	0	1
Upwards	753	450	0.11	0.31	0	1
<i>Time-invariant predictors</i>						
Lower-sec. track						
Low requirements	1203	0	0.06	0.24	0	1
Medium requirements	1203	0	0.26	0.44	0	1
Comprehensive	1203	0	0.23	0.42	0	1
High requirements	1203	0	0.45	0.50	0	1
Upper-sec. track						
VET with low or medium intellectual requirements	1038	165	0.37	0.48	0	1
VET with high intellectual requirements/vocational bacc.	1038	165	0.28	0.45	0	1

Academic baccalaureate school	1038	164	0.34	0.47	0	1
<hr/> <i>Time-invariant controls</i>						
SES: parents with tertiary education (ref. sec. education)	1190	13	0.29	0.46	0	1
School performance	1881	22	4.60	0.50	1.00	6.00
Employed at wave 4	1203	0	0.26	0.44	0	1
Gender	1203	0	0.46	0.50	0	1
Basic cognitive abilities	1203	0	3.32	1.46	0	6
Migration background	1201	2	0.13	0.33	0	1

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**Table 2: Analysis of sample attrition:
Comparison of participants and non-participants of the the 4th wave**

Variable	n	df	Chi-Square	p-value
Lower-sec. track (ref. high)				
Low requirements	1203	1	24.70	0.000
Medium requirements	1203	1	8.07	0.005
Comprehensive	1203	1	0.32	0.569
High requirements	1203	1	27.80	0.000
Upper-sec. track				
VET with low or medium intellectual requirements	1038	1	8.44	0.004
VET with high intellectual requirements/vocational bacc.	1038	1	0.94	0.332
Academic baccalaureate school	1038	1	4.17	0.041
SES: parents with tertiary education (ref. sec. education)	1190	1	6.01	0.014
Gender	1203	1	0.26	0.610
Migration background	1201	1	39.90	0.000
	n	df	t-test	p-value
ISEI	1132	1130	2.975	0.003
School performance	1181	1179	2.979	0.003
Basic cognitive abilities	1203	1201	3.676	0.000

Table 3: Multilevel models predicting the level and the development of occupational status aspirations

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Figure 1: Main pathways between secondary and higher education in the Swiss educational system

Source: Own illustration, simplified version

Figure 2: Development of occupational status aspirations by upper-secondary track

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Highlights

- The level of occupational aspirations is strongly linked to secondary school track
- Opposing developmental trends are observed for general education and VET
- Irregular track changes are accompanied by an adjustment of aspirations
- Individual development is linked with educational opportunities

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